

LUMPY SKIN DISEASE: AN OVERVIEW

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ABSTRACT

LUMPY SKIN DISEASE is caused by capri pox virus, that was reported at first in India in year 2020 in Orissa state, then spread to other regions of India, has the significant morbidity and less mortality, but significant economic loss due to appearance of hide in leather industry and loss of milk production due to the decrease in appetite.

KEYWORDS: Morbidity, Mortality, Capri pox virus.

INTRODUCTION

LUMPY SKIN DISEASE (LSD) is caused by Capripox virus that causes significant morbidity in cattle (10-20%), mortality rate is low around 1-5%, economic losses result from loss of condition, decreased milk production, abortions, infertility and damaged hides. LSD is endemic in most of the African countries, originally originated from Zambia in 1929 and later on spread to Zimbabwe, Mozambique and south Africa. In the year 2012 it has spread rapidly through the middle east, Southeast Europe, Balkans, Caucasus, Russia and Kazakhstan. Outbreaks reported in other countries are Bangladesh (July 2019), India (Aug 2019), China (Aug 2019), Vietnam (Oct 2020), Bhutan (Oct 2020), Hong kong (Nov 2020) Nepal (Jul, 2020). In India the 1st outbreak was reported to the OIE from Orissa on 12/08/2019 which on PCR phylogenetic analysis is found that the strains were closely related to that of South African N12490/KSGP like strain.

EPIDEMIOLOGY

Morbidity rate varies between 10 - 20%, Mortality rate varies from 1-5%. Mortality in various states of India are highest are in Rajasthan followed by Maharashtra, Karnataka and Punjab (Govt of India, Department of Animal Husbandary and Dairying)

INCIDENCE

In Cattle the incidence is 30.8%, Buffaloes the incidence is 1.6%, In Arabian Orynx the incidence is 1.0%, In Giraffe the incidence is 1.05, In Impala the incidence is 1.0%, In Yak the Incidence is 1.0%.

Hosts:

LSD virus is highly host specific and causes diseases only in cattle (*Bos indicus* and *Bos taurus*) and water Buffaloes (*Bubalus bubalis*). Local Zebu cattle are more resistant to disease than the cross breed cattle. LSD virus is non zoonotic.

Animal Transmission:

Primary route: Biting insects: Mosquitoes, Biting flies, Male ticks. Rarely transmission is by nasal discharge, contaminated feed and water. Movement of live animals, direct contact is ineffective means of transmission.

Virus:

Family: Poxviridae, Genus: Capri pox virus, closely related to sheep and goat pox, very sturdy virus, recovered from skin nodules kept at -80°C for 10 years and infected tissue culture fluid stored at 4°C for 6 months. The virus is susceptible to acidic or alkaline P.H. The virus is susceptible to ether (20%), chloroform, formalin(1%) , detergents like sodium dodecyl sulphate, also susceptible to phenol (2%) for 15 minutes, sodium hypochlorite(2-3%), iodine compounds (1:33